

Cyclodextrin mediated non-aqueous electrophoresis for chiral separations of anionic boron clusters

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ARTICLE INFO

Handling editor: Agata Michalska

Keywords:

Boron clusters
Cyclodextrins
Non-aqueous capillary electrophoresis
Chiral separations
Carboranes
Separation efficiency
bis(dicarbollide)
nido-carborane

ABSTRACT

Anionic boron cluster compounds have recently made their way into many areas including medicinal chemistry and sensors due to favorable physical-chemical properties and their various biological activity. Notwithstanding the inherent chirality of these compounds, the exploration of the properties and activity of individual enantiomers remains uncharted territory. The permanent delocalized negative charge enables the electrophoretic mobility of these compounds. Thus, chiral electrophoresis, characterized by minimal consumption of chemicals and a sample, emerges as a promising candidate for a reliable quality control tool. The primary attempts in aqueous electrolytes showed some difficulties related to the limited solubility of these analytes. This study meticulously investigates the electrophoretic behavior and chiral separation of anionic [7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₁]⁻ and cobalt bis(dicarbollide)(1-) derivatives using a methanolic non-aqueous electrolyte with numerous derivatives of cyclodextrins. Randomly substituted hydroxypropyl-β-, methyl-β-, and hydroxypropyl-γ-cyclodextrins were identified as the most effective chiral selectors. The chiral separations delineated herein surpass previously published results in capillary electrophoresis in terms of resolution, peak shape, and the number of theoretical plates. Furthermore, the application of (2-hydroxy-3-*N,N,N*-trimethylamino)propylated β-cyclodextrin in non-aqueous environment resulted in the chiral separation of seven recently synthesized amino cobalt bis(dicarbollide)(1-) derivatives; thereby, reinforcing the extensive applicability of the developed methodology for different structural types of anionic cobalt bis(dicarbollides)(1-). These results qualify non-aqueous electrophoresis as a valuable tool for the enantiomeric purity control of anionic boron cluster compounds with respect to their further use in various areas.

1. Introduction

Boron cluster compounds (BCC) are purely synthetic inorganic species. Their distinctive 3D structure is formed due to the existence of a three-center two-electron bond among boron atoms due to only two electrons available for three inner skeletal orbitals [1]. Dodecaborane (2-) ([B₁₂H₁₂]²⁻) represents a highly symmetric and remarkably stable structure [2]. However, the icosahedral symmetry in heteroboranes and metallaheteroboranes may be impaired due to one or more of the following processes: endohedral substitution with other atom(s) or groups, notional deboronation or modification with exoskeletal groups

(Fig. 1). Consequently, these compounds exhibit chirality, despite the absence of a discrete center of asymmetry [3,4].

BCC possess unique properties based on their structure. These properties, such as thermal and chemical stability, catalytic and electrochemical activity, and the ability to store hydrogen, predetermine BCC to be attractive for various applications [1,2,5]. Thus, BCC have been used as high-energy fuels [6], boron delivery compounds in boron neutron capture therapy (BNCT) [7], an agent in the treatment of radioactive waste [2,6] or as a stationary phase for gas chromatography [2]. Particularly promising are cobalt bis(dicarbollide) ([Co(C₂B₉H₁₀)₂]⁻) and dicarbollide ion ([7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₀]²⁻), which have been used in radionuclide extraction [8], design of advanced materials,

This article is part of a special issue entitled: Electroanalysis published in Talanta.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2025.128117>

Received 3 September 2024; Received in revised form 7 April 2025; Accepted 8 April 2025

Available online 10 April 2025

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Abbreviations:

ACN	acetonitrile
AcOH	acetic acid
BCC	boron cluster compounds
BGE	background electrolyte
CD	cyclodextrin
CE	capillary electrophoresis
HPLC	high-performance liquid chromatography
MeOH	methanol
NACE	non-aqueous capillary electrophoresis
NH ₄ Ac	ammonium acetate
NMR	nuclear magnetic resonance
SFC	supercritical fluid chromatography
Tris	tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane

electrochemistry or conducting polymers [9,10]. These compounds are currently being investigated in medicinal chemistry, e.g., BNCT of tumors [11], the development of antitumor drugs [12–14]. Their other use in chemistry involves potential homogenous stereoselective catalysts or their constituents [15,16], modifiers of nanostructured materials for drug delivery [17], tools for improving the activity of therapeutic peptides [18], potential fluorescent agents for cell tracking [19], additives to polymers [20], switchable luminescent materials [21], and chiral sensors [22].

The specific structure and chromatographic behavior of BCC do not enable the direct transfer of chiral methods used for the separation of organic compounds. Therefore, all chiral selectors must be thoroughly tested on the representative panel of BCC. Thus, polysaccharide-based chiral selectors were tested in HPLC [23] and SFC [24] and vancomycin- and cyclofructan-based chiral selectors were used for chiral separation in HPLC [25]. Although different chiral selectors were used in HPLC and SFC, native CDs are to date the only option for chiral separation of these compounds in CE [26]. Recent chiral separation of a few anionic species using native β -CD [27], brominated β -CD [28], and 2-hydroxypropylated β -CD [25] confirmed the usefulness of cyclodextrins (CDs) in chiral separations of BCC in HPLC. Over the past two decades, there has been a growing interest in the development of new CE methods for the achiral [29–31] and particularly chiral analysis of anionic BCC [31–35]. Although CE is fundamentally unsuitable for preparative or semipreparative purposes, it is an excellent tool for assessing chiral purity.

The previous articles dealing with chiral separations of BCC using aqueous-organic background electrolytes (BGE) are summarized in Table 1. Native α -, β - and γ -CD were investigated for chiral separation of ten diverse anionic BCC. The authors emphasized the importance of the presence of an organic solvent in the BGE to improve the solubility of the clusters and reduce seemingly irreversible interactions between

Table 1

Summary of the successfully separated [7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₁]⁻, [(1,2-*closo*-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-3-Co]⁻, [(1,7-*closo*-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-2-Co]⁻, and [i-B₁₈H₂₁]⁻ to this date [26, 29,31–35].

Groups of compounds	The most suitable chiral selector	Formulas of separated compounds (anionic parts)
<i>nido</i>-7,8-C₂B₉H₁₂(1-)	native α -CD	[5-Br-7,8- <i>nido</i> -C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁] ⁻ [7-CH ₃ -7,8- <i>nido</i> -C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁] ⁻ [7-C ₆ H ₅ -7,8- <i>nido</i> -C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁] ⁻ [7-CH ₃ S-7,8- <i>nido</i> -C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁] ⁻ [7-NCS-7,8- <i>nido</i> -C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁] ⁻ [9-CH ₃ S-7,8- <i>nido</i> -C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁] ⁻ [7-C ₂ H ₅ S-7,8- <i>nido</i> -C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁] ⁻ [7-(2'-pyridyl)-7,8- <i>nido</i> -C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁] ⁻ [7-C ₆ H ₅ -8-C ₆ H ₅ S-7,8- <i>nido</i> -C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀] ⁻ [7-CH ₃ -8-C ₆ H ₅ S-7,8- <i>nido</i> -C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀] ⁻ [7-Pyridine-8-C ₂ H ₅ S-7,8- <i>nido</i> -C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀] ⁻ [7-Pyridine-8-C ₃ H ₇ S-7,8- <i>nido</i> -C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀] ⁻
bridged cobalt bis(1,7-C₂B₉H₁₁)(1-)	native β -CD	[6,6'- μ -S-(1,7-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀) ₂ -2,2'-Co] ⁻
bridged cobalt bis(1,2-C₂B₉H₁₁)(1-)	native β -CD	[8,4',8',4- μ -(C ₆ H ₄) ₂ -Co(1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₉) ₂] ⁻ [4,8'; 8,4'- μ -(tolyl) ₂ -Co(1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₉) ₂] ⁻ [4,8'; 8,4'- μ -(ethylphenyl) ₂ -Co(1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₉) ₂] ⁻
unbridged cobalt bis(1,2-C₂B₉H₁₁)(1-)	native β -CD	[4,4'- μ -(HS)-2-(1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₉) ₂ -3-Co] ⁻

hydrophobic anionic analytes and β -CD under purely aqueous conditions [31,34]. ACN was originally considered to be a better organic solvent than methanol (MeOH) due to its positive effect on enantioselectivity and shorter migration times because of the lower viscosity in mixtures with water [31]. Later, ACN was disputed as an organic additive because of the continuous decrease in the effective mobilities of analytes over time. The authors explained this phenomenon by the degradation of the native CDs and consecutive interactions of degradants with the anionic analytes. They also theorized that a similar process takes place while MeOH is present in BGE, however, it progresses much slower [34,35]. Native β -CD was found to be the most universal chiral selector that separates compounds from all investigated classes [34]. However, chiral separation of [7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₁]⁻ derivatives was also achieved using native α -CD [34,35]. Native γ -CD was disqualified for further use due to the low solubility in BGE containing 75 % MeOH (v/v) and the time-dependent decrease in the effective mobilities of BCC. In summary, six enantiomers from twelve tested were baseline separated, reaching resolution from 1.5 to 6.2. Two analytes substituted with the -SCH₃ group were resolved with exceptional R_s values of 13.6 and 27.6 [35].

Chiral NACE (Non-Aqueous Capillary Electrophoresis) is a

Fig. 1. The symmetry impairment in the cage of dodecaborane. Endohedral substitution of dodecaborane(2-) ([B₁₂H₁₂]²⁻) results in the 1,2-*closo*-dicarbadodecaborane (1,2-*closo*-C₂B₁₀H₁₂). The [7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₁]⁻ is produced by subsequent deboronation. In the end, the symmetry is further lowered due to the introduction of an exoskeletal substituent not only to the boron atom 9 as illustrated, but also to carbon atoms and other boron atoms [3,4]. The last molecule is chiral. The boron and carbon atoms are colored green and black, respectively. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for the sake of clarity. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

complementary technique to chiral aqueous CE, where different diastereomeric complexes are formed due to distinct intermolecular interactions [36]. The high solubility of anionic cobalt bis(dicarbollide) (1-) derivatives and $[7,8\text{-nido-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11}]^-$ derivatives in MeOH makes them excellent candidates for chiral separations in NACE. Importantly, reduced generation of Joule heat in NACE allows the use of higher voltage resulting from lower current, which might improve chiral discrimination [37]. This could lead to a decrease in migration times, in contrast to that of aqueous CE, while maintaining good reproducibility. Despite the suggestion to study the chiral separation in non-aqueous media [33], to the best of our knowledge, we present the first chiral separation of anionic BCC in NACE. The group of $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})_2]^-$ and $[7,8\text{-nido-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11}]^-$ derivatives (see Fig. 2) was selected to demonstrate the capability of NACE using randomly derivatized CDs as chiral

selectors. Comprehensive information covering resolution, migration times, electrophoretic mobility, and separation efficiency of enantiomers is discussed for each compound with respect to the optimal separation conditions. The results contribute to a better understanding of the chiral separation of BCC under NACE conditions and enhance the capabilities of CE as a promising candidate for a reliable quality control tool, where the enantiomeric ratio is significant for their further use.

2. Experimental

2.1. Chemicals

The $[7,8\text{-nido-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11}]^-$ derivatives (Fig. 2), i.e., $[5\text{-Br-}7,8\text{-nido-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11}]\text{.Cs}$ (1), $[9\text{-Br-}7,8\text{-nido-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11}]\text{.Cs}$ (2), $[7\text{-CH}_3\text{-}7,8\text{-nido-}$

Fig. 2. Structures of the analyzed compounds.

C₂B₉H₁₁].Cs (3), [7-C₆H₅-7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₁].(CH₃)₄N (4), [5-C₆H₅-7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₁].Cs (5), [9-NCS-7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₁].Cs (6), [9-CH₃S-7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₁].Cs (7); and the cobalt bis(dicarbollide)(1-) derivatives (Fig. 2), i.e., [6,6'-μ-S-(1,7-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-2,2'-Co].Cs (8), [8,8'-μ-S₂-(1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-3,3'-Co].Cs (9), [8,4',8',4-μ-bis(C₆H₄)₂-(1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-3,3'-Co].Na (10), [1-(HO(CH₂)₂-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)-3,3'-Co].(CH₃)₃NH (11), [1-(HO(CH₂)₂)₂-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)-3,3'-Co].(CH₃)₃NH (12), [1-(HO(CH₂)₃-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)-3,3'-Co].(CH₃)₃NH (13), [1,1'-(HOCH₂-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-3,3'-Co].(CH₃)₃NH (14), [1,1'-(HO(CH₂)₂-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-3,3'-Co].(CH₃)₃NH (15), [8,8'-μ-O-(1-HO(CH₂)₃-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)-3,3'-Co].(CH₃)₃NH (16), [8,8'-μ-O-(1,1'-(HO(CH₂)₃)₂-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-3,3'-Co].(CH₃)₃NH (17), [1-(HCl.H₂N(CH₂)₂-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co].(CH₃)₄N (18), [1,1'-(HCl.H₂N(CH₂)₂-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-3,3'-Co].(CH₃)₄N (19), [1-(H₂N)-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co].(CH₃)₄N.HCl (20), [1,1'-(H₂N)₂-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-3,3'-Co].(CH₃)₄N.2HCl (21), [1-(HCl.H₂NCH₂)-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co].(CH₃)₄N.HCl (22), [1,1'-(HCl.H₂NCH₂)-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-3,3'-Co].(CH₃)₄N (23), [1,1'-μ-HN-(CH₂-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-3,3'-Co].(CH₃)₄N (24), [1-(HCl.H₂N(CH₂)₃)-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co].(CH₃)₄N (25); were used in this study. The references to the syntheses of all compounds are given in Supporting material.

Chemicals for BGE preparation were of LC-MS grade: MeOH 99.9 % (Avantor International, Czech Republic), ammonium acetate (NH₄Ac) ≥99.99 %, 2-amino-2-(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-propanediol (Tris) ≥99.8 % (Merck, Germany), and *ortho*-phosphoric acid 85 % (Penta, Czech Republic). NH₄Ac was stored in a desiccator. Other chemicals used were sodium hydroxide 97.0 % (Penta, Czech Republic), acetic acid HPLC grade ≥99.8 % (AcOH) (Merck, Germany), boric acid p.a. (Lachner, Czech Republic), and ultrapure Milli-Q water (Millipore purification system, Merck-Millipore, Germany).

Native α-CD ≥98 % and β-CD ≥97 % were purchased from Merck, Germany. The semi-synthetic CDs were obtained from Cyclolab, Hungary. CDs are listed with their abbreviations and the average degree of substitution measured with NMR by the producer (abbreviation, degree of substitution). Randomly methylated α-CD (Me-α-CD, 10.9), randomly methylated β-CD (Me-β-CD, 11.2), randomly methylated γ-CD (Me-γ-CD, 10.9), randomly 2-hydroxypropylated α-CD (HOPr-α-CD, 5.4), randomly 2-hydroxypropylated β-CD (HOPr-β-CD, 4.2), randomly 2-hydroxypropylated γ-CD (HOPr-γ-CD, 5.3), randomly (2-hydroxy-3-*N,N,N*-trimethylamino)propylated α-CD (cationic α-CD, 2.2), randomly (2-hydroxy-3-*N,N,N*-trimethylamino)propylated β-CD (cationic β-CD, 3.0), randomly (2-hydroxy-3-*N,N,N*-trimethylamino)propylated γ-CD (cationic γ-CD, 3.4), and randomly acetylated β-CD (Ac-β-CD, 7.3).

2.2. Sample and BGE preparation

All samples were dissolved in 100 mmol/L NH₄Ac solution in MeOH to reach a concentration of 0.2 mg/mL. For the preparation of non-aqueous BGE, a 100 mmol/L NH₄Ac solution in MeOH was prepared. In the case of MeOH-aqueous mixture-based BGE, the required ratio *v/v* of MeOH and water was mixed and subsequently, the weighted amounts of H₃BO₃, H₃PO₄ and Tris, or H₃PO₄ and Tris were dissolved to obtain the required molar concentration. Then, the calculated amount of the respective CD was weighed and subsequently added to the mixture to reach the required molar concentration. The concentrations of the Me-α-CD (1, 10, 30, and 50 mmol/L); Me-β-CD (1, 10, 30, 50, and 100 mmol/L); Me-γ-CD (1, 5, 10, and 30 mmol/L); HOPr-α-CD, HOPr-β-CD, HOPr-γ-CD (1, 10, 30, 50, and 100 mmol/L); cationic α-CD (1, 2.5, 5, 10, 20, 30, and 50 mmol/L); cationic β-CD (1, 2.5, 5, 10, 20, and 30 mmol/L); and cationic γ-CD (0.1, 1, 2.5, 5, and 10 mmol/L) were chosen according to their solubility in BGE, time of analysis of individual analytes, and number of successfully separated enantiomers.

2.3. CE instrumentation and calculations

The CE 7100 electrophoretic instrument (Agilent Technologies,

Germany) equipped with a DAD detector, with an air-controlled capillary temperature compartment was employed for the study. The bare silica capillary of i.d. 75 μm and o.d. 365 μm (Microsolvy, USA) was used for the analysis. The capillaries were of 53 cm long with an effective length of 44.5 cm. The voltage of 25 kV and -25 kV were applied for the measurements with MeOH-aqueous-based BGEs. All analyses in non-aqueous conditions were carried out in negative polarity, -12.5 kV was applied. The injection of the sample was done by applying a pressure of 50 mbar for 3 s. The temperature of the capillary compartment was controlled at 25 °C. The derivatives of [7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₁]⁻ and cobalt bis (dicarbollide)(1-) were detected at wavelengths 210 and 290 nm, respectively. The newly prepared capillary was flushed with 0.1 mmol/L NaOH, water, and 1 % AcOH in MeOH and MeOH for 600 s each. Between analyses, the capillary was flushed with BGE for 120 s. The capillary was stored in water. Before each sample set analysis, the capillaries were flushed with water, 1 % AcOH in MeOH, MeOH, and finally BGE for 120 s, 300 s, 300 s, and 300 s, respectively. The flushing steps with MeOH were not used for the analysis in MeOH-aqueous-based BGE.

Resolution (Rs) values were calculated based on the current Ph. Eur. i.e., $R_s = 1.18 \times \frac{t_{R2} - t_{R1}}{W_{0.5h1} + W_{0.5h2}}$, where *t*_{R2} and *t*_{R1} are migration times of the second and the first enantiomer, respectively, and *w*_{0.5h1} and *w*_{0.5h2} are peak widths at a half height of the first and second eluting enantiomer, respectively. The values of *w*_{0.5h1} and *w*_{0.5h2} of the peaks coeluting over 50 % of their height were estimated from their integration. This means that Rs values below 0.8 are slightly biased for symmetrical peaks and more influenced for tailing peaks.

3. Results and discussion

In previous papers, polyacrylamide-coated capillaries were preferred for chiral separations of BCC to eliminate electroosmosis [31–33,35]. The coating process is laborious with batch-to-batch variations affecting the reproducibility of the whole analytical procedure. Therefore, we focused on the development of the chiral methods using native α- and β-CDs without coating the capillary wall. The following results in MeOH-aqueous BGE were achieved: (1) native β-CD is not suitable for chiral separations in positive polarity (Table S1) due to the broad and tailing peaks (Fig. S1); (2) no peak tailing was observed in negative polarity (Fig. S2), which resulted in a significant improvement in resolution (Table S2); (3) the use of native α-CD in negative polarity resulted in chiral separations of four from seven anionic [7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₁]⁻ with resolution >1.5 (Table S3 and Fig. S3); even some cobalt bis(dicarbollides)(1-) were partially separated with resolution always lower than 1.10; (4) although the use of native α-CD in negative polarity reduced the analysis time by 50 % compared to native β-CD, the broad peaks were still present; switching to positive polarity solved even this issue and further halved the separation time in case of anionic [7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₁]⁻ 1, 3, 6, and 7 (Fig. S4).

In summary, cobalt bis(dicarbollides)(1-) were discriminated into enantiomers with Rs < 1.5 (except for analytes 10 and 14) and unsatisfactory migration times (around 1 h). Under the same conditions, derivatives of [7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₁]⁻ were separated with resolution between 0.53 and 11.30 and migration times around 30 min. However, challenging [7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₁]⁻ 2, 4, and 5 remained only partially separated or unseparated.

3.1. Chiral separation in NACE

Application of a non-aqueous environment to chiral separations of BCC is only a logical step owing to their very good solubility in organic solvents, weakening of strong interactions between BCC and CDs, and possibly even a different mechanism of chiral recognition compared to MeOH-aqueous BGEs [37,38]. Another advantage is the very simple preparation of a BGE. The suppression of the electro-osmotic flow due to

the presence of a non-aqueous environment and high molarity of NH_4Ac is another advantage that could result in chiral separations with shorter analysis time [36]. The analytes and NH_4Ac are soluble in MeOH unlike native α -, β -, and γ -CD. Therefore, the modified CDs were used to circumvent this issue. In contrast to HPLC [4], only the randomly acetylated β -CD provided no successful chiral separation. The first experiments in BGE consisted of MeOH- NH_4Ac (100 mmol/L) with different amounts of selected chiral selectors using a voltage of -25 kV often resulted in capillary clogging. Therefore, the voltage was lowered to -12.5 kV, decreasing the current, Joule heat, and ensuring longer life of capillaries, i.e., more than 1000 injections per capillary.

The effect of CD cavity on chiral separations of BCC - discussion about whether BCC enters the cavity in a water-organic environment did not result in a clear conclusion [35]. The authors suggested that for a deeper understanding of the chiral separation behavior of BCC,

evaluation of chiral separation in non-aqueous capillary electrophoresis (NACE) is necessary. In NACE, preferably the interactions of the compounds with the hydroxy groups at the rim of the CDs are expected [36, 37]. When an inclusion complex of an analyte with CDs is not formed, the migration times should be similar despite the changes in the cavity size. However, this is not the case for the analyzed derivatives of [7, 8-*nido*- $\text{C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11}$] $^-$ and cobalt bis(dicarbollide)(1-) derivatives. The compounds migrated differently at the same molar concentrations of α -, β -, γ -CDs bearing the same substituents (Fig. 3). Hence, the migration times decreased in order γ -CD > β -CD > α -CD for most analytes (1, 3, 5, 6, 8, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15). This observation shows that the strength of the CD-analyte interaction decreases in the same order, confirming previous studies of CD interactions with similar compounds in NMR [38,39]. Furthermore, the migration time of all compounds increases with the concentration of each CD (see Fig. 3 for compounds 3, 7, 13, and 17 and

Fig. 3. Effect of the molar concentration of CDs on the migration time of the first enantiomer (M_{t1}) of compounds 3 and 7 of [7,8-*nido*- $\text{C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11}$] $^-$ derivatives and compounds 13 and 17 of cobalt bis(dicarbollide)(1-) derivatives. The connecting lines do not show a trendline; they are depicted to enhance the readability of the figure. Empty symbols denote no chiral separation, full symbols stand for $R_s > 0$.

Figs. S5 and S6, and S7 for other compounds). A more gradual increase of migration times was observed for per-Me- β -CD and all employed α -CDs and small differences in the migration times were found. These small variances are negligible compared to the difference in the migration times among α -, β -, and γ -CD derivatives. Therefore, the results suggest the inclusion of studied BCC into a cavity stabilized by hydroxy groups on the rim of randomly substituted β - and γ -CDs even in the presence of 100 mmol/L of NH_4Ac . Some compounds deviated from this phenomenon and the migration times decreased in order β -CD > γ -CD > α -CD. Thus, longer migration times of compounds **4**, **7**, **10**, **16**, and **18** were observed using Me- β -CD and cationic- β -CD than their γ -CD variants. Moreover, no clear trends were observed for the analyte **17**. These observations suggest a possibility of a different mechanism of chiral recognition by CDs. The concentration of CD in BGE affected the resolution of the enantiomers according to the theory and it reached the maximum at the specific value and then decreased usually in order γ -CD > β -CD > α -CD (Fig. S8). These results confirm the high strength of the complex analytes-CDs and correspond with the previously reported high affinities of BCC for β -CD similar to adamantane [38].

The effect of separation efficiency on chiral separations of BCC - it was previously described that there is a decrease in separation efficiency for BCC with the addition of native CD to an aqueous-organic BGE. The authors pointed out that this is in contradiction to the behavior of 'classical' organic compounds [29,31,35]. To further investigate this phenomenon the number of theoretical plates with and without various CDs in the BGE was analyzed. Both the decrease and increase in number of theoretical plates with the addition of CDs were observed. Therefore, the decrease in separation efficiency of BCC with the addition of CD is not a general phenomenon as previously suggested. It strongly depends on the type of CD and the type of the analyzed compound (Figs. S9 and S10). As the interaction of the BCC with the CD cavity is very strong [38,39], the interaction kinetics will be slower, and the separation efficiency will decrease. This is probably the reason why Vespalec et al. observed the decrease of separation efficiency in aqueous-organic BGE [33]. In our case, the methanolic non-aqueous environment decreases the affinity of BCC toward the CD cavity, enabling the enhancement of the separation efficiency for Me- β -CD, Me- γ -CD, HOPr- α -CD, HOPr- β -CD, HOPr- γ -CD, and cationic α -CD for the most analytes.

Chiral separation of cobalt bis(dicarbollide)(1-) derivatives - HOPr- γ -CD was the chiral selector of choice for unbridged hydroxy alkylated cobalt bis(dicarbollides)(1-) (compounds **11**–**15**) that reached baseline separations in all cases (Fig. 4). It should be noted that disubstituted analytes **14** and **15** were separated more often and with higher resolution compared to monosubstituted hydroxyalkyl derivatives **11**–**13**, see Fig. 5. This phenomenon can be explained by a higher number of interactions between CD and hydroxy groups on both dicarbollide(2-) subunits.

Comparison of chiral separations of unbridged (**13**) and oxygen-bridged (**16**) hydroxypropyl cobalt bis(dicarbollide)(1-) shows the involvement of the oxygen bridge in a separation mechanism. The enantiomers of compound **13** were separated at baseline using HOPr- γ -CD but the analyte **16** was not separated by any γ -CDs (Fig. 6). It appears that the oxygen bridge prevents compound **16** from forming an enantioselective complex with any γ -CDs despite their larger cavities. On the contrary, the disubstituted oxygen-bridged compound **17** was successfully separated by HOPr- γ -CD and cationic γ -CD probably due to the presence of two hydroxypropyl moieties. The cobalt bis(dicarbollide)(1-) bridged with sulfur (**8**) and bisphenylene (**10**) were at least partially separated using eight tested CDs. Although the best chiral selectors for compounds **8** and **10** are HOPr- γ -CD and Me- β -CD, respectively, multiple chiral selectors can be chosen for the baseline separation of these compounds (see Fig. 5).

The method development should be started with MeOH- NH_4Ac (100 mmol/L) as BGE, the voltage of -12.5 kV, and the capillary compartment maintained at 25 °C. The HOPr- γ -CD (10, 50, and 100

mmol/L) is recommended particularly for hydroxy alkylated cobalt bis(dicarbollides)(1-). The cationic- β -CD (1, 20, and 30 mmol/L) was useful for the separation of all cobalt bis(dicarbollides)(1-) except for compound **9** (no chiral discrimination was observed under any tested conditions). Besides both above-mentioned CDs, HOPr- β -CD (100 mmol/L) and Me- β -CD (30 or 100 mmol/L) are also worth testing. Very high resolution (11.35) was achieved for bisphenylene-bridged compound **10** using 100 mmol/L Me- β -CD bringing the possibility to separate compounds with similar structures.

Chiral separation of [7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₁]⁻ derivatives - the highest number of separated compounds was achieved using HOPr- γ -CD and Me- β -CD. However, using HOPr- β -CD the higher resolution values were reached (Fig. 5). Compounds **3**, **5**, **6**, and **7** were chirally discriminated using 100 mmol/L (compounds **3**, **5**, **6**) or 200 mmol/L (compound **7**) HOPr- β -CD obtaining resolution values of 1.13, 1.80, 1.56, and 1.24, respectively. The concentration of CD is also an important factor that determines the price of the analysis. Therefore, a simple change of the chiral selector can save a significant number of resources. For example, the chiral separation of compound **3** using 30 mmol/L Me- β -CD instead of 100 mmol/L HOPr- β -CD results in a similar resolution of 1.16 and a separation time of 25 % shorter. In addition to neutral CDs, chiral separations were also achieved using positively charged CDs. However, the zones were significantly wider compared to neutral ones (see Fig. 4, Table S4). Therefore, cationic CDs are not generally recommended for the chiral separations of these anionic carboranes.

Interestingly, the partial chiral discrimination of two challenging compounds (**1** and **4**) was achieved more frequently using γ -CDs, when HOPr- γ -CD appears to be the best. These observations only underline the importance of non-aqueous media since previous experiments in MeOH-aqueous-based BGEs using native γ -CD were unsuccessful [26]. According to the results (Fig. 5), the bulkiness of the substituent clearly plays a role in chiral recognition in non-aqueous BGE. The place of substitution and thus the shape of the molecule are also important. When a bulky phenyl ring is substituted on boron at position 5 (compound **5**), then the chiral separation is more probable compared to substitution on carbon at position 7 (compound **4**). In contrast, when the substituent on carbon in position 7 is less bulky, e.g., the methyl group (compound **3**) then there is a higher probability of separating enantiomers. Another example represents compounds **1** and **2** with bromine substituted on boron at positions 5 and 9, respectively. Contrary to multiple chiral separations of compound **1**, compound **2** was not separated under any tested conditions. In contrast, other *nido*-derivatives substituted at position 9, with the -SCN group (compound **6**) and the -SCH₃ group (compound **7**) were prone to chiral discrimination.

The method development should begin with MeOH- NH_4Ac (100 mmol/L) as BGE, the voltage of -12.5 kV, and the capillary compartment maintained at 25 °C. The HOPr- γ -CD (10, 50, and 100 mmol/L); HOPr- β -CD (100 mmol/L); and Me- β -CD (30 or 100 mmol/L) are recommended as a starting point. It must be noted that chiral separations could be also carried out on a bare silica capillary with MeOH-aqueous BGE. The native α -CD (25 or 5 mmol/L) provided very high values of resolution for compounds **1**, **3**, **6**, and **7** (Fig. 4B). The starting conditions include MeOH-(H₃BO₃-Tris, 100 mmol/L-70 mmol/L buffer) (40:60 or 30:70, v/v) as BGE, voltage 25 kV, and 25 °C. According to our results, these conditions are suited for derivatives with small substituents, i.e., methylthio, thiocyanato, bromine or methyl.

Chiral separation of amino cobalt bis(dicarbollide)(1-) derivatives - finally the separation conditions for cobalt bis(dicarbollides)(1-) were tested on their amino derivatives, which have been recently introduced as valuable building blocks for synthesis with tunable pKa values [40]. Based on the protonation/deprotonation of the amino group the electrophoretic mobility as well as the interactions with the CDs are considerably affected. Primarily, the compound **18** with the ethylamine group was baseline separated using 30 mmol/L Me- β -CD (Rs 3.40), 20 mmol/L cationic- α -CD (Rs 3.74), 1 mmol/L cationic- β -CD (Rs 3.75), and 5 mmol/L cationic- γ -CD (Rs 3.10) (Fig. 5). Given the low

A) NACE (BGE in MeOH)

B) Combined organic-aqueous CE (BGE in H₂O-MeOH mixture)

Fig. 4. Electropherograms with the baseline resolution or the highest resolution of the enantiomers are presented in the shortest possible time. The color of the trace is assigned according to the chiral selector used as follows: green - HOPr- γ -CD, cyan - HOPr- β -CD, blue - Me- β -CD, red - cationic- α -CD, purple - cationic- β -CD, and black - α -CD. The electrophoretic conditions of non-aqueous (A) and MeOH-aqueous (B) capillary electrophoresis including compositions of the BGE are presented in Table S4. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. The effect of the type of CD on resolution (A) is shown. The molar concentration of a CD is shown only for partial or baseline chiral separations (B). $R_s < 1.00$; $1.00 \leq R_s \leq 1.50$; and $R_s > 1.50$ are colored orange, light green, and dark green, respectively. The red fields indicate no chiral separation. For the chemical formulae of analytes and CDs, see Fig. 2 and the Experimental section. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 6. Comparison of the chiral separations of unbridged hydroxypropyl cobalt bis(dicarbollide)(1-) **13** (blue trace) and oxygen-bridged hydroxypropyl cobalt bis(dicarbollide)(1-) **16** (green trace) using 100 mmol/L HOPr- β -CD and 100 mmol/L HOPr- γ -CD. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

consumption of chiral selector while maintaining high resolution cationic- β - and γ -CD were tested for chiral discrimination of other amino derivatives **19–25**. The highest selectivity and resolution were achieved with cationic- β -CD resulting in successful chiral separations of all compounds except for **23** (Fig. 7). Although cationic γ -CD was also able to discriminate the same enantiomers, broad triangular peaks were observed for most of the compounds precluding its further use. The separation of a broad range of compounds with very different pKa values [40] using cationic- β -CD further confirms the broad applicability of the developed methods.

4. Conclusions

The current study brings a new complementary approach to traditional methods such as HPLC and SFC for evaluation of chiral purity of anionic boron clusters. These compounds are being studied in various areas including medicinal chemistry, electrochemistry, and material science. The use of NACE surpasses previously published results in terms

of resolution, peak shape, and separation efficiency. It is ascribed to the better solubility of these compounds in methanol, higher number of available CDs, and presence of favorable interactions between analytes and a chiral selector. The further studies of interactions between CDs and anionic BCC revealed that the strength of the complex CD-analyte decreases in order γ -CD > β -CD > α -CD and these compounds enter the cavity of the CDs even in NACE conditions. The investigation of the effect of separation efficiency on concentration of CDs showed that it is not always lowered with the addition of CD as was originally thought. It was shown to be compound dependent and both increase/decrease were found. The three CDs of choice were HOPr- β -CD, Me- β -CD and HOPr- γ -CD. The HOPr- γ -CD is suitable for successful chiral separations of 78 % of compounds **1** to **18** (of which 56 % were baseline separated). While the resolution of [7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₁]⁻-based enantiomers was comparatively lower, it was sufficiently high for determining enantiomeric purity or confirming racemic character for the most derivatives. Nevertheless, [7,8-*nido*-C₂B₉H₁₁]⁻ derivatives exhibited optimal separation in a MeOH-aqueous BGE with native α -CD, except for a derivative bearing a phenyl group in position 5 (compound **5**) which achieved the highest resolution with HOPr- β -CD in non-aqueous MeOH BGE. Additionally, the developed methodology for cobalt bis(dicarbollides)(1-) was applied to their amino derivatives and resulted in the baseline separation of six from seven compounds with cationic β -CDs. This fact underscores the potential of NACE with CDs as a robust tool for the chiral separation of cobalt bis(dicarbollide)(1-) derivatives. The advancement of chiral separation techniques is a significant step towards the application of chiral boron clusters in various fields where molecular configuration is critical.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ondřej Horáček: Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Lukáš Lochman:** Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Kristýna Linková:** Investigation. **Ece Zeynep-Tüzün:** Investigation. **Bohumír Grüner:** Resources. **Radim Kučera:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources.

Fig. 7. Electropherograms with the baseline resolution of the amino bis(dicarbollide)(1-) derivatives. All compounds were analyzed in MeOH-NH₄Ac (100 mmol/L) using cationic- β -CD (5 mmol/L). The voltage -12.5 kV was applied, and the temperature of 25 °C. The peaks of enantiomers of respective compound are marked by asterisks.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The research was supported by research project “New Technologies for Translational Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences” (NETPHARM), project ID CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004607, co-funded by the European Union and Charles University (SVV 260 666).

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2025.128117>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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